

On a conjecture involving the function $SL^*(n)$

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Abstract In this paper, we define a new arithmetical function $SL^*(n)$, which is related with the famous F.Smarandache LCM function $SL(n)$. Then we studied the properties of $SL^*(n)$, and solved a conjecture involving function $SL^*(n)$.

Keywords F.Smarandache LCM function, $SL^*(n)$ function, conjecture.

§1. Introduction and result

For any positive integer n , the famous F.Smarandache LCM function $SL(n)$ is defined as the smallest positive integer k such that $n \mid [1, 2, \dots, k]$, where $[1, 2, \dots, k]$ denotes the least common multiple of all positive integers from 1 to k . For example, the first few values of $SL(n)$ are $SL(1) = 1$, $SL(2) = 2$, $SL(3) = 3$, $SL(4) = 4$, $SL(5) = 5$, $SL(6) = 3$, $SL(7) = 7$, $SL(8) = 8$, $SL(9) = 9$, $SL(10) = 5$, $SL(11) = 11$, $SL(12) = 4$, $SL(13) = 13$, $SL(14) = 7$, $SL(15) = 5$, $SL(16) = 16$, \dots . From the definition of $SL(n)$ we can easily deduce that if $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots p_r^{\alpha_r}$ be the factorization of n into primes powers, then

$$SL(n) = \max\{p_1^{\alpha_1}, p_2^{\alpha_2}, \dots, p_r^{\alpha_r}\}.$$

About the elementary properties of $SL(n)$, many people had studied it, and obtained some interesting results, see references [2], [4] and [5]. For example, Murthy [2] proved that if n be a prime, then $SL(n) = S(n)$, where $S(n)$ be the F.Smarandache function. That is, $S(n) = \min\{m : n \mid m!, m \in N\}$. Simultaneously, Murthy [2] also proposed the following problem:

$$SL(n) = S(n), \quad S(n) \neq n? \tag{1}$$

Le Maohua [4] solved this problem completely, and proved the following conclusion:

Every positive integer n satisfying (1) can be expressed as

$$n = 12 \quad \text{or} \quad n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots p_r^{\alpha_r} p,$$

where p_1, p_2, \dots, p_r, p are distinct primes and $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_r$ are positive integers satisfying $p > p_i^{\alpha_i}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, r$.

Zhongtian Lv [5] proved that for any real number $x > 1$ and fixed positive integer k , we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} SL(n) = \frac{\pi^2}{12} \cdot \frac{x^2}{\ln x} + \sum_{i=2}^k \frac{c_i \cdot x^2}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right),$$

where c_i ($i = 2, 3, \dots, k$) are computable constants.

Now, we define another function $SL^*(n)$ as follows: $SL^*(1) = 1$, and if $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots p_r^{\alpha_r}$ be the factorization of n into primes powers, then

$$SL^*(n) = \min\{p_1^{\alpha_1}, p_2^{\alpha_2}, \dots, p_r^{\alpha_r}\},$$

where $p_1 < p_2 < \cdots < p_r$ are primes.

About the elementary properties of function $SL^*(n)$, it seems that none has studied it yet, at least we have not seen such a paper before. It is clear that function $SL^*(n)$ is the dual function of $SL(n)$. So it has close relations with $SL(n)$. In this paper, we use the elementary method to study the following problem: For any positive integer n , whether the summation

$$\sum_{d|n} \frac{1}{SL^*(n)}, \quad (2)$$

is a positive integer? where $\sum_{d|n}$ denotes the summation over all positive divisors of n .

We conjecture that there is no any positive integer $n > 1$ such that (2) is an integer. In this paper, we solved this conjecture, and proved the following:

Theorem. There is no any positive integer $n > 1$ such that (2) is an positive integer.

§2. Proof of the theorem

In this section, we shall complete the proof of the theorem directly. For any positive integer $n > 1$, let $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots p_r^{\alpha_r}$ be the factorization of n into primes powers, from the definition of $SL^*(n)$ we know that

$$SL^*(n) = \min\{p_1^{\alpha_1}, p_2^{\alpha_2}, \dots, p_r^{\alpha_r}\}. \quad (3)$$

Now if $SL(n) = p_k^{\alpha_k}$ (where $1 \leq k \leq r$) and n satisfy

$$\sum_{d|n} \frac{1}{SL^*(d)} = N, \quad \text{a positive integer,}$$

then let $n = m \cdot p_k^{\alpha_k}$ with $(m, p_k) = 1$, note that for any $d|m$ with $d > 1$, $SL^*(p_k^i \cdot d) \mid m \cdot p_k^{\alpha_k - 1}$, where $i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, \alpha_k$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} N &= \sum_{d|n} \frac{1}{SL^*(d)} = \sum_{i=0}^{\alpha_k} \sum_{d|m} \frac{1}{SL^*(d \cdot p_k^i)} = \sum_{i=0}^{\alpha_k} \frac{1}{SL^*(p_k^i)} + \sum_{i=0}^{\alpha_k} \sum_{\substack{d|m \\ d>1}} \frac{1}{SL^*(d \cdot p_k^i)} \\ &= 1 + \frac{1}{p_k} + \cdots + \frac{1}{p_k^{\alpha_k}} + \sum_{i=0}^{\alpha_k} \sum_{\substack{d|m \\ d>1}} \frac{1}{SL^*(d \cdot p_k^i)}, \end{aligned}$$

or

$$m \cdot p_k^{\alpha_k - 1} \cdot N = \sum_{i=0}^{\alpha_k} \sum_{\substack{d|m \\ d>1}} \frac{m \cdot p_k^{\alpha_k - 1}}{SL^*(d \cdot p_k^i)} + m \cdot p_k^{\alpha_k - 1} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{1}{p_k} + \cdots + \frac{1}{p_k^{\alpha_k - 1}} \right) + \frac{m}{p_k}. \quad (4)$$

It is clear that for any $d|m$ with $d > 1$,

$$\sum_{i=0}^{\alpha_k} \sum_{\substack{d|m \\ d>1}} \frac{m \cdot p_k^{\alpha_k - 1}}{SL^*(d \cdot p_k^i)} \quad \text{and} \quad m \cdot p_k^{\alpha_k - 1} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{1}{p_k} + \cdots + \frac{1}{p_k^{\alpha_k - 1}} \right),$$

are integers, but $\frac{m}{p_k}$ is not an integer. This contradicts with (4). So the theorem is true. This completes the proof of the theorem.

Open problem. If $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots p_r^{\alpha_r}$ be the factorization of n into primes powers, whether there exists an integer $n \geq 2$ such that $\sum_{d|n} \frac{1}{SL(n)}$ is an integer?

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